

3. Ярова О.А. Збірник задач з теорії ймовірностей та математичної статистики: Навчальний посібник. – Київ: Прінтту, 2026, 88 с.

І.О. Деменко,

Post-graduate student of the Laboratory of Problems of Applied Informatics

Д.І. Симонов

PhD, Head of the Laboratory of Problems of Applied Informatics

V. M. Glushkov Institute of Cybernetics of the National Academy of Sciences of
Ukraine

STATISTICAL MODELING AND RESOURCE OPTIMIZATION IN MULTI-AGENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS

Modern information systems operate under increasing complexity of digital processes, growing data volumes, and higher requirements for processing speed. Distributed environments, intelligent digital platforms, decision support systems, and real-time services require efficient use of computational and information resources. Under these conditions, resource optimization in multi-agent information systems becomes especially relevant, since agents autonomously perform operations, interact with one another, and adapt their behavior to the current state of the environment. Similar issues of bottlenecks, resource limitations, and information flow optimization are considered in studies on data-flow models and complex information systems [1-2].

Multi-agent approaches enable parallel execution of operations, increase system scalability, and accelerate the achievement of target states. However, without effective coordination, agents may duplicate actions, distribute workload unevenly, and consume excessive resources. This reduces overall productivity and complicates system functioning under uncertainty. Therefore, the development of statistical models for analyzing agent behavior, evaluating coordination mechanisms, and determining rational modes of resource use is an important scientific task. The relevance of such modeling is also confirmed by studies on multi-component dynamic systems and stochastic resource allocation problems [3; 4].

A multi-agent information system can be considered as a stochastic dynamic environment in which agents perform operations, move between states, and use shared resources. State changes are probabilistic and depend on both local agent actions and interaction mechanisms. Within this approach, statistical modeling aims to determine coordination strategies that reduce duplication, improve resource efficiency, and increase the integral effectiveness of the system. This problem is

close to multi-criteria selection of information processing schemes, where several conflicting indicators must be considered simultaneously [5].

To formalize the coordination process, an integral efficiency functional of a multi-agent system is used:

$$J(\Pi) = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T \lambda^t (\alpha F_t - \beta C_t - \gamma D_t) \right], \quad (1)$$

where F_t characterizes the functional performance of the system at time t , C_t is the intensity of resource consumption, D_t is the level of duplicated operations between agents, Π is the set of agent interaction strategies, λ is the discount factor, and α , β , γ are the weight coefficients of the corresponding components. This formulation makes it possible to consider agent coordination as a multi-criteria optimization problem, within which it is necessary to ensure a compromise between system productivity, resource costs, and redundancy of performed operations [4; 5].

For a comprehensive statistical evaluation of the efficiency of a multi-agent system, the following integral criterion is used:

$$Q(T) = \theta_1 \Phi_R(T) - \theta_2 \Phi_D(T) + \theta_3 \Phi_C(T) - \theta_4 \sigma_R^2(T), \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi_R(T)$ is the efficiency of resource use, $\Phi_D(T)$ is the level of duplicated operations, $\Phi_C(T)$ is the degree of coordination consistency between agents, $\sigma_R^2(T)$ is the variance of resource distribution among agents, and θ_i are the weight coefficients of the criteria. The proposed criterion makes it possible to simultaneously take into account system productivity, balanced resource use, the level of agent coordination, and losses caused by redundant operations.

To verify the proposed approach, computer modeling of a multi-agent information system functioning in a stochastic state space with a clustered structure was carried out. Within the experiment, three agent interaction strategies were compared: independent operation without coordination, static coordination, and adaptive coordination. The main attention was paid to the evaluation of Φ_R , Φ_D , Φ_C , and the integral criterion $Q(T)$ (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of the efficiency of agent interaction strategies in a multi-agent information system

The obtained results demonstrate a clear advantage of adaptive coordination. Independent agent operation shows the lowest resource efficiency ($\Phi_R \approx 0.22$) and the highest duplication level ($\Phi_D \approx 0.72$). Static coordination improves these indicators: Φ_R increases to approximately 0.47, while Φ_D decreases to 0.33. The best results are achieved by adaptive coordination, where resource efficiency reaches $\Phi_R \approx 0.78$, and the duplication level decreases to $\Phi_D \approx 0.08$.

Coordination consistency also confirms the advantage of the adaptive strategy: Φ_C increases from approximately 0.44 for independent operation to 0.74 for static coordination and 0.91 for adaptive coordination. The integral criterion $Q(T)$ shows the same trend: 0.21, 0.52, and 0.84, respectively. This indicates that considering the current state of the environment and the history of agent interaction substantially improves the efficiency of a multi-agent information system.

Thus, statistical modeling confirms the feasibility of adaptive coordination for resource optimization in multi-agent information systems. The proposed approach reduces operation duplication, improves agent interaction consistency, and ensures more rational resource use. Its practical value lies in its applicability to intelligent digital platforms, distributed information environments, decision support systems, and other complex information systems.

References

1. Kruk R. A., Zhukovska N. A. Analysis of bottleneck points based on the software requirements data-flow model in Agile projects. *Mathematical Modeling and Computing*. 2025. Vol. 12, No. 2. P. 628–639.
2. Aftabi N., Moradi N., Mahroo F., Kianfar F. An integrated system dynamics and agent-based modeling framework for information security management in complex information systems with multi-actor threat dynamics. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 2024.
3. Symonov D. I., Zaika B. Y., Symonov Y. D. Multi-output regression models for controlling multi-component dynamic systems. *Tavriyskyi Scientific Bulletin. Series: Technical Sciences*. 2024. No. 6. P. 106–119.
4. Symonov D. I. Algorithm for determining the optimal flow in Supply Chains, considering multi-criteria conditions and stochastic processes. *Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Physics and Mathematics*. 2021. No. 2. P. 109–116.
5. Popov M., Zaitsev O., Stefantsev S. An analytical approach to multi-criteria choosing technological scheme for information processing. *Radio Electronics, Computer Science, Control*. 2025. No. 4. P. 202–208.

Т.Є. Терещенко,

Доцент кафедри фінансів банківської справи та страхування, к.е.н., доцент

Д.Д. Басараб

Здобувач вищої освіти

Університет митної справи та фінансів

СТАТИСТИЧНА ОЦІНКА СТАНУ РОЗВИТКУ МАЛОГО БІЗНЕСУ В УКРАЇНІ

Розвиток малого підприємництва є фундаментальною умовою формування гнучкої та конкурентоспроможної економічної системи країни. Малий бізнес є важливим інструментом забезпечення стійкості державних фінансів. Спрощена система оподаткування, обліку та звітності дозволяє залучати мільйони громадян до самозайнятості, створюючи стабільні джерела доходів як для домогосподарств, так і для місцевих бюджетів через сплату єдиного податку, ПДФО та військового збору. У період макроекономічної нестабільності саме малий бізнес демонструє найбільшу мобільність, диверсифікуючи ризики та наповнюючи дохідну частину бюджету держави в умовах воєнних та повоєнних викликів.